

DETERMINANTS OF SHAREHOLDER VALUE OF MOTOR VEHICLES AND INTANGIBLE ASSETS: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIAN DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS (2014–2024)

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of asset structure on shareholder value: a study of selected Nigerian deposit money banks. The goals of this study were to ascertain the effects of motor vehicles and other intangible assets on shareholder value in Nigerian deposit money banks. With the adoption of an ex post facto research design, the study used the population of all listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, with a special focus on seven banks (Access, Fidelity, Guarantee Trust, First, Union, Zenith Banks, and United Bank for Africa) from which the samples were selected. From the conducted Hausman test, the fixed-effects model was more reliable, hence its usage in examining the relationships. Results of multiple regression analysis carried out with the aid of E-View 13 revealed a statistically significant effect of motor vehicle ($\beta = 0.350000$; $p < 0.05$) and intangible assets ($\beta = 0.175487$; $p < 0.05$) on the value of the deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Therefore, the study concluded that intangible assets, such as intellectual property, goodwill, and proprietary technologies, are important in driving financial performance and creating value for shareholders. Therefore, we recommend that deposit money banks continue investing in motor vehicles to enhance transportation and logistics efficiency, which plays a crucial role in marketing and operational effectiveness as well as shareholder returns.

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1.1 Introduction

In shaping any company's financial performance and long-term value creation, the assets structure of such a company has a major role to play (Emengini et al., 2023). According to Madukwe et al. (2022), the configuration and utilization of both tangible and intangible assets are key determinants of shareholder value in Nigeria's financial service sector. This is because the sector is considered to have high capital intensity and a slippery and dynamic operational environment. While some studies, such as Ullah and Ahmad (2019), Onwaeze and Osuji (2024), Onuigbo and Okafor (2024), and Odoh et al. (2025), have focused heavily on land, buildings, and production equipment, there is a growing need to understand the contribution of other asset components, particularly motor vehicles and intangible assets, to the overall equity value of deposit money banks operating in Nigeria. This is because depositors cannot be comfortable with leaving their monies in the DMBs without substantial goodwill. Reaching out to convince depositors requires a reasonable investment in motor vehicles for easy access and mobility.

According to Manafa (2023), motor vehicles, which are often classified under transportation or logistics assets, are primarily essential to enhancing the efficiency of large entities, such as the DMBS. These deposit money banks mainly rely on a robust fleet for personnel movement, distribution, and marketing activities, especially given Nigeria's infrastructural limitations. Despite their utility, motor vehicles are frequently underrepresented in asset value assessments due to their rapid depreciation rate and frequent replacement cycles (Madukwe et al., 2022). However, when efficiently managed, they contribute to cost savings, logistics enhancement, and ultimately improved financial returns. Hence, empirically examining how investments in motor vehicles influence shareholders' funds is a compelling reason.

In Nigeria's deposit money banks' (DMBs) competitive strategies, intangible assets such as goodwill, patents, licenses, proprietary technologies, and trademarks are becoming increasingly relevant (Etoko & Igisi, 2024). To Onuigbo and Okafor (2024), these assets, though non-physical, often provide long-term economic benefits by enhancing innovation, brand reputation, and regulatory compliance. However, their valuation is often complex, and their impact on the performance of deposit money banks is not always immediately evident in financial statements. In Nigeria, where intangible asset recognition and measurement under IFRS are still evolving, many DMBS struggle to accurately capture the value of these resources (Adika, 2015; Ezekwesili & Afodigbueokwu, 2021). This creates a gap in understanding how such assets contribute to shareholder wealth and whether they should be prioritized in corporate investment decisions.

The Nigerian banking sector continues to experience shifts owing to technological advancements, regulatory reforms, and global environmental pressures. These changes necessitate a re-evaluation of asset structures beyond the traditional categories. Stakeholders increasingly demand evidence that all assets, both tangible and intangible, are being deployed in ways that enhance DMB' valuation and shareholder equity. Unfortunately, limited empirical research exists on how specific asset types such as motor vehicles and intangible assets affect shareholder value in Nigeria as a developing economy (Akpeekon, 2021).

1.2 Study Problem

Nigeria's DMBs must prioritize not only the acquisition but also the strategic management of their asset structure to improve shareholder value and long-term competitiveness. This includes tangible assets such as motor vehicles and intangible assets such as patents, licenses, and goodwill. When efficiently utilized and properly accounted for, these asset classes can drive operational effectiveness, enhance firm valuation, and ultimately increase shareholders' fund. Therefore, corporate managers are expected to optimize the performance of all asset components, not only core infrastructure but also those that indirectly support production and value creation.

However, notwithstanding the operational importance of both motor vehicles and intangible assets, they are frequently underrepresented in empirical financial analyses and undervalued in corporate balance sheets (Aseinimieyefori, 2022). Owing to their short useful lives and rapid depreciation, motor vehicles are often

categorized as low-impact assets, even though they form the logistical lifeline of many deposit money banks. Similarly, intangible assets, including regulatory permits, brand equity, and technical know-how, are not always properly recognized or measured, particularly under inconsistent IFRS practices in Nigeria. This often results in a misalignment between asset investment and RSV. As observed by Manafa et al. (2023), companies may invest heavily in these assets but fail to see a corresponding reflection in equity performance due to poor utilization or inadequate financial disclosure. Previous studies on deposit money banks have not isolated motor vehicles and intangible assets as separate predictors of shareholders' funds via panel regression.

On the basis of the above, this study deemed it necessary to critically examine the effect of motor vehicles and intangible assets on the value of shareholders in Nigeria's DMBs. Hence, the study is guided by two specific objectives:

- i. To ascertain the effects of motor vehicles on the value of shareholders in Nigeria's deposit money banks
- ii. To ascertain the effects of intangible assets on the value of Nigeria's deposit money banks to shareholders

This study contributes to the fixed asset valuation debate in the Nigerian banking sector in two areas that have not received the required attention. Based on these areas, the study raised and answered the following two research questions:

- iii. What are the effects of motor vehicles on the value of shareholders in Nigeria's deposit money banks?
- iv. What are the effects of intangible assets on the value of Nigeria's deposit money banks?

1.3 Development of the Study Hypotheses

According to Egwu et al. (2023) and Etoko and Igisi (2024), the assets of any company help it generate the required inflows that can be used to secure favorable funding of the necessary outflows. According to Onuigbo and Okafor (2024), the acquisition of assets in the deposit money banks requires a huge capital outlay. Hence, caution must be exercised because excess investment in either non-current, current, or even intangible assets can tie down the resources needed for investment in others, thereby making the company suffer in the area of assets neglected. Insufficient investment in non-current assets, such as motor vehicles or intangible assets, can hinder productivity and patronage, thereby reducing the required inflow.

Hence, studies such as Mawih (2014), Duru et al. (2017), Charlie and Akpan (2020), Orbunde et al. (2023), Uduji and Okolo-Obasi (2023), Onwaeze and Osuji (2024), Pukon (2024), and Odoh et al. (2025) all agreed that an appropriate mix of assets is all that is required to enable company management to achieve a competitive edge and better performance. Conversely, in Nigeria's banking sector, the asset management mix remains a subject matter that is not clearly defined. To this, the actual effect of non-current assets, such as motor vehicles, and intangible assets, such as goodwill, patents, licenses, and trademarks, on the value of shareholders cannot be said to be known with total conviction. Based on this, the current study, while considering motor vehicles and intangible assets of deposit money banks in Nigeria, hypothesized the following:

- Motor vehicles does not have a significant effect on the value of shareholders (book value) in Nigeria's deposit money banks.
- Intangible assets do not have a significant effect on the value (book value) of shareholders in Nigeria's deposit money banks.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Perspective

2.1 Literature Review

Asset structure

Asset structure refers to the composition and proportion of different assets classes—both tangible and intangible, within a firm's balance sheet. It includes how resources, such as land, buildings, machinery, and motor vehicles, and intangible assets, such as goodwill or licenses, are distributed to support operations and generate value (Orbunde et al., 2023). The configuration of these assets significantly influences a DMB's capacity to generate returns, manage risks, and enhance shareholder wealth, especially in asset-heavy sectors such as DMBs (Onuigbo

& Okafor, 2024). According to Duru et al. (2017), Charlie and Akpan (2020) and Okolo-obasi et al (2025), a balanced asset structure is critical for aligning operational efficiency with financial stability. Firms can achieve cost control, scalability, and long-term profitability when they allocate resources strategically among productive assets (Pukon, 2024). However, if asset allocation favors underutilized or rapidly depreciating assets without generating corresponding income, shareholders' value may be eroded. Madukwe et al. (2022) stress that DBMs with poorly managed fixed assets tend to underperform in terms of capital efficiency and shareholder return metrics. Conversely, banks that maintain an optimized asset mix often report stronger equity positions and market confidence.

The concept of asset structure extends beyond ownership to include valuation and utilization (Emengini et al., 2023). Adika (2015) explains that firms can adopt different valuation models (cost or fair value) under IFRS, which affect how assets are reported and perceived. Therefore, asset structure not only reflects investment strategy but also signals corporate governance and financial health. Mawih (2014) and Manafa et al. (2023) further emphasized that asset misclassification or insufficient disclosure may distort investors' perception and lead to undervaluation or excessive risk exposure. In the Nigerian banking context, where banks operate under volatile regulatory and economic conditions, having a resilient and productive asset structure is essential. This includes recognizing the value of both tangible assets such as motor vehicles and intangible assets such as licenses and IP. Understanding asset structure is fundamental to assessing how effectively a DMB transforms its resources into shareholder value.

Motor Vehicles

Motor vehicles form an integral part of tangible non-current assets and play a crucial role in deposit money banks' operational architecture. They are generally categorized as transportation or logistics assets and are used for the conveyance of personnel, materials, and finished products (Enekwe et al., 2023). In a country like Nigeria, where infrastructure challenges often disrupt supply chains, a well-maintained fleet of motor vehicles is essential for the smooth execution of operational activities. Although not directly involved in production, these assets indirectly contribute to value creation by supporting service delivery and logistical efficiency (Madukwe et al., 2022). Despite their importance, motor vehicles are often undervalued in financial analysis due to their relatively short useful lives, wear and tear susceptibility, and high maintenance costs. Manafa et al. (2023) noted that the failure to efficiently manage and account for logistics-related assets can result in capital misallocation and lower asset turnover ratios, which in turn reduce shareholder returns. Conversely, DMBs that implement effective FMPs, including scheduled maintenance, timely replacement, and optimal usage, stand a better chance of realizing operational savings that improve profitability and shareholder value.

Under the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), motor vehicles are recognized as property, plant, and equipment (PPE) and are measured at a cost less accumulated depreciation and impairment losses. Their depreciation is typically calculated using the straight-line method, which spreads the cost over the estimated useful life of the asset (Adika, 2015). The accounting treatment affects not only the net book value of the assets but also the firm's reported earnings and shareholders' equity. In deposit money banks, the strategic relevance of motor vehicles goes beyond mobility. They help mitigate marketing and operational downtime, support field activities, and facilitate product distribution, especially in regions with limited infrastructure. As such, these assets should not be viewed as mere logistics tools but as contributors to cost efficiency and, ultimately, shareholder wealth (Onuigbo & Okafor, 2024).

Intangible Assets

Intangible assets are non-physical, identifiable resources that provide firms with economic benefits over time (Aggelopoulos et al., 2016). These include intellectual property such as patents, trademarks, software, goodwill, franchises, licenses, and proprietary technologies. In the deposit money banks, intangible assets are increasingly becoming a key driver of value through innovation, regulatory compliance, brand strength, and operational rights

(Adika, 2015; Akpeekon, 2021). Unlike tangible assets, intangible assets do not have a physical form but play a critical role in supporting firms' core and support functions in complex and regulated environments, such as Nigeria's banking sector (Awa et al., 2020; Gozie-Onu et al., 2024). According to Okolo-obasi et al (2025), governing recognition and measurement of intangible assets is the IAS 38 under the IFRS. These standards require that intangible assets be identifiable, the firm must control them, and future economic benefits must be probable. Externally acquired intangible assets are usually capitalized, whereas internally generated assets, except for development costs, are often expensed, creating inconsistencies in financial reporting across firms (Ezeana & Ezeagba, 2024). This variability contributes to the challenges in assessing the full impact of IVAs on firm performance and shareholder value.

The under-recognition of intangible assets in financial reports can distort oil and gas firms' equity valuations. According to Chukwu et al. (2017) and Manafa et al. (2023), failure to adequately disclose or measure intangibles such as licenses and operational rights limits investors' ability to accurately assess the firm's true asset base and potential. In a sector driven by technology, legal access, and strategic partnerships, intangibles often represent competitive advantage and long-term income streams. Moreover, Charlie and Akpan (2020) and Onuigbo and Okafor (2024) assert that firms with higher investment in intangible assets tend to exhibit stronger brand equity and regulatory standing, which contribute to long-term shareholder value. However, the direct link between intangible assets and shareholder funds is often underexplored in empirical literature, particularly within the Nigerian context, due to their abstract nature. Thus, intangible assets are not only instruments of innovation but also essential components of asset structure that deserve deeper analysis to understand their true impact on the wealth of shareholders in capital-intensive sectors such as deposit money banks.

Shareholder Value

Shareholders' value, also referred to as shareholder fund or equity, represents the owners' residual interest in a firm after all liabilities have been deducted from total assets (Egwakhe et al., 2023). It comprises paid-up share capital, retained earnings, reserves, and other comprehensive income. In essence, it reflects shareholders' wealth and serves as a critical measure of financial health, performance, and corporate sustainability (Onuigbo & Okafor, 2024). In capital-intensive sectors such as banking, shareholders' funds are particularly important because they indicate how effectively a firm converts its asset base, both tangible and intangible, into long-term value for its owners. According to Egwu et al. (2023), despite substantial asset holdings, asset-heavy firms that fail to strategically manage their investments may experience stagnant or declining shareholder equity. This underscores the need for asset accumulation, efficient utilization, and alignment with profitability and growth goals.

The growth of shareholders' funds largely depends on a firm's ability to generate profits, reinvest in high-return projects, and effectively manage capital (Egwakhe et al., 2023). When firms allocate resources to productive assets, such as value-adding intangible resources or strategically utilized motor vehicles, these investments are expected to reflect in increased earnings, retained profits and, ultimately, shareholder wealth. However, as noted by Manafa (2023) and Etoko and Igisi (2024), the mere possession of large assets does not guarantee value addition unless these assets are fully operationalized and managed for maximum output. Moreover, the reporting and valuation of assets under IFRS significantly influence the perceived and actual size of shareholders' funds. Adika (2015) and Kornom-Gbaraba et al. (2024) observed that inconsistent asset valuation practices, particularly in the recognition of intangible assets, can distort the real economic value attributable to shareholders, thereby affecting investor confidence and share pricing. Thus, shareholders' fund is a key indicator of whether a bank's asset structure, capital strategy, and operational activities are aligned with shareholders' wealth maximization goals. In sectors such as financial services, where both physical and intangible assets are substantial, tracking their influence on shareholders' equity is critical for financial decision-making and long-term sustainability.

Asset Valuation and Depreciation under International Financial Reporting Standards

Under the IFRS, the valuation and depreciation of non-current assets, including tangible items such as motor vehicles and intangible assets such as goodwill and licenses, are governed by clear but flexible principles. These standards are designed to enhance consistency, transparency, and comparability in financial reporting, especially across capital-intensive industries such as DMBs (Egwu et al., 2023). IAS 16 provides guidelines for valuing tangible assets, such as motor vehicles. After initial recognition at cost, these assets can be carried using either the cost model, where they are measured at cost less accumulated depreciation and impairment, or the revaluation model, where they are carried at fair value less depreciation (Nangih & Emeka-Nwokeji, 2021). Depreciation, which is most commonly calculated using the straight-line method, is essential for matching the asset's cost with its economic benefits over time. High depreciation rates for motor vehicles reflect their limited useful life and wear from operational use, which directly impacts their book value and, by extension, equity reports.

IAS 38 governs intangible assets. Intangible assets must be identifiable, controlled by the entity, and expected to generate future economic benefits. While externally acquired intangible assets are capitalized, most internally generated assets are expensed unless they meet stringent recognition criteria during the development phase. This creates variations in how different firms report their intangible resources, which sometimes leads to understated asset values and distorted shareholder funds (Manafa et al., 2023). The choice between cost and fair value models, combined with varied depreciation and amortization practices, directly influences the net asset value, profit margins and, ultimately, shareholders' equity. Aggelopoulos et al. (2016) and Pukon (2024) noted that many Nigerian firms struggle with the consistent application of IFRS standards, particularly regarding the recognition and impairment of intangible assets. These inconsistencies affect comparability across banks and create gaps in investor understanding and confidence.

Capital Asset Management in Deposit Money Banks

Capital asset management refers to the strategic acquisition, maintenance, utilization, and optimization of long-term assets, such as machinery, motor vehicles, and intangible assets—that are essential for a firm's operational effectiveness and financial sustainability. Capital asset management is particularly vital in deposit money banks due to the capital-intensive and asset-heavy nature of the banking industry (Manafa, 2023). These banks depend on substantial fixed and intangible assets to support production, logistics, regulatory compliance, and market competitiveness (Onuigbo & Okafor, 2024). Effective capital asset management ensures that both tangible and intangible resources are adequately maintained and fully utilized to deliver operational benefits and maximize shareholder value. Madukwe et al. (2022) noted that banks that fail to manage their corporate assets efficiently often experience asset underperformance, increased operating costs, and reduced equity returns. This risk is especially significant for assets such as motor vehicles, which depreciate quickly and require continuous servicing and monitoring to remain productive.

Moreover, intangible assets, such as intellectual property and licenses, which represent non-physical but economically valuable resources, also require deliberate management strategies. These include safeguarding ownership rights, timely renewals, legal compliance, and alignment with innovation and branding goals. According to Manafa et al. (2024), the absence of proper systems to track and evaluate the economic contribution of intangibles can lead to underreporting and missed opportunities for equity enhancement. Capital asset management extends beyond the physical functionality of assets to include valuation, lifecycle costing, and alignment with strategic corporate goals in deposit money banks' operations. Adika (2015) highlights that improper application of asset valuation and impairment principles under IFRS can misrepresent a bank's true capital position, resulting in misleading conclusions about its financial health and shareholder equity. Therefore, capital asset management is not merely a technical function but a strategic imperative. For firms operating in volatile and resource-driven sectors, such as deposit money banks, the efficiency of capital asset management directly influences shareholder value, operational resilience, and long-term competitiveness.

Empirical Review

Etoko and Igisi (2024) investigated the asset structure and financial performance of marketing firms in Nigeria between 2014 and 2023. Specifically, the study ascertained the relationship that exists between asset structure and financial performance. Asset structure was represented by the current asset to non-current asset (CA/NCA) ratio, while financial performance was measured in terms of ROE and ROCE. The study adopted a descriptive correlational research design. A sample of five firms was drawn from the population of eight listed firms in the industry to conduct the study. The investigation employed descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, the Durbin-Watson test, and regression testing to analyze the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms. Statistical test results showed that an insignificant relationship exists between the current asset to non-current asset (CA/NCA) ratio and return on equity (ROE), and that an insignificant relationship exists between the CA/NCA ratio and return on capital employed (ROCE).

In their study, Egwu, Ohachosim, and Itah (2023) examined the effect of investment in non-current assets on the performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Secondary data were collected from the annual reports and accounts of the 15 selected quoted firms for the period of eight (8) years spanning from 2012 to 2019. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analyses. The empirical results revealed that investment in tangible non-current assets has a positive and significant effect on the selected manufacturing firms' return on assets (ROA). Investment in intangible non-current assets also has a positive and significant effect on the return on assets. The debt-to-assets ratio has a positive and significant effect on the return on assets, whereas the asset turnover ratio has a negative but insignificant effect on the return on assets.

Ezekwesili and Afodigbueokwu (2021) conducted a study to determine the relationship between capital structure and the wealth of industrial good firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study ascertained the effect of short- and long-term debts on the wealth of shareholders. The study employed an ex-post facto research design. Coefficient of correlation and Panel Least Squares regression analysis with the aid of E-Views 9.0 was used to analyze the data obtained based on the empirical evidence from 2008 to 2020. The analysis revealed that a short-term debt ratio has a significant positive relationship with the cash value added of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria at the 5% level of significance, and a long-term debt ratio has a significant and positive relationship with industrial goods firms in Nigeria at the 5% level of significance.

Pukon (2024) conducted a recent study to analyze the effect of intangible assets on Nigeria's financial sector performance. The study used an ex-post facto research design and employed a panel least squares regression analysis. The study used current data on the amortization of intangible assets, total investment in intangible assets, and earnings per share obtained from the annual report of two (2) major Banks (UBA and First Bank from 2018 to 2022). Panel least squares analysis indicated that the amortization of intangible assets and the total investment of intangible assets have a positive but insignificant effect on the listed banks' earnings per share in Nigeria.

Orbunde, Arumona, and Akintoye (2023) investigated the impact of IAI on the business viability of Nigerian deposit money institutions. The investigation employed an ex-post facto design with a sample size of 12 institutions that deposit money. The analysis used secondary data obtained from the Nigerian Exchange Group between 2012 and 2021. The random effect regression analysis technique was used to analyze the data, and the results indicated that goodwill intensity has a significant positive effect on sustainable growth rate, whereas asset intangibility intensity has a significant negative effect on the sustainable growth rate of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Akpeekon (2021) examined the effect of intangible assets on the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria and the moderating effect of ownership structure on the relationship between deposit money banks and financial performance. Data were collected from the annual reports of five listed commercial banks over a period of 6 years (2012-2017). We proxied intangible assets with goodwill, whereas financial performance was measured using return on assets. The study used the ex-post facto research design and conducted regression analyses to test

two hypotheses raised for the study. The findings showed that intangible assets have a significant negative effect on profitability, but managerial ownership had an insignificant moderating effect on the relationship between intangible assets and firm performance.

2.2 Theoretical Underpinning

Financing constraint theory

This work is underpinned by the financing constraint theory propounded by Goldratt in 1990 to contend that organizations that do not make profit do not have a support to contribute and do not have the capacity to back their development or possibly their supportability, and will at long last vanish. Here, the cradle is the held income, which will be little if the organization does not make a profit or chooses to allot most its profit to shareholders. The FCT is the study of the impact of financial frictions on the firm's investment. It is one of the most important cornerstones of corporate finance. The FCT theory hinges on the theoretical underpinnings that encompass the information-driven problems of studying a company's investment under incentive restriction(s). These are cradle equivalents to the inside capital, or, in other words, the outer capital, as indicated by the pecking request theory. Put in another way, the theory expresses that the organizations that produce benefit and then hold it benefit themselves of good development openings, while the organizations that have no or low benefits cannot profit from great investment openings, so they do not develop quickly (Jang & Park, 2011). Audretsch and Elston (2012) are connected to this line of reasoning when they stress the significance of the impact of firm size on the relationship between gainfulness and development. They thought about firm size as a dynamometer, which estimates the relationship between gainfulness and development. As indicated, a reduction in firm size debilitates the benefit effect on development. Additionally, Wagenvoort (2013) expressed that little firms will confront more financial misery, hampering the development of these organizations. Bechetti and Trovato (2012) and Carpenter and Petersen (2012) believed that constraints generally influence the development of small firms. In contrast, larger firms will confront less financial constraints and are more likely to be exempted to shield gainfulness. Thus, bigger firms will abuse productivity more precisely and significantly, prompting more investments and a snappier development process. Therefore, Financing Constraint Theory posits that firms, particularly in capital-intensive sectors such as oil and gas, often face challenges in raising funds, either due to external market conditions or internal financial restrictions. These constraints can significantly influence a firm's investment in non-current assets, which in turn affects shareholders' equity.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Ex post facto research design was chosen for this study to empirically solve the research problems using secondary data. Hence, the published financial statements of the selected deposit money banks in Nigeria were the main data source for the analysis.

3.2 Study Area

We conducted the study in Nigeria with a particular focus on the deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NEG) for a period of 10 years (2014–2024).

3.3 Sources of Data

Secondary data were the main data source based on the nature of this study. The source of data for the study was secondary. The secondary data suggested a content analysis of historical economic events and business transactions that were reported on the utilization of non-current (motor vehicles) and intangible assets to justify the effect of deposit money banks on shareholder value. The data were collected from the published annual reports and accounts of the deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The independent variables of the study include: motor vehicle and intangible assets, while the dependent variable is the selected companies' shareholder value.

3.4 Study Population

The study population comprises seven deposit money banks listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group as at 31st December, 2024. These companies include Access, Fidelity, Guarantee Trust, First, Union, Zenith Banks, and United Bank for Africa.

3.5 Determination of Sample Size

Out of all the Nigerian DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, seven were purposively drawn out of the total population. The purpose of selecting the seven banks was to ensure that such banks have national coverage and have operated for over 10 years. Hence, we had 77 (77) observations. The selected sample size guaranteed high accuracy and reliability. The sampled banks are: Access, Fidelity, Guarantee Trust, First, Union, Zenith Banks, and United Bank for Africa.

3.6 Data Analysis Method

Multiple regression analysis was used to test the study's research hypotheses. We adopted the regression analysis because of the need to use a mathematical equation to express the nature of the relationship that exist between variables and ultimately to use this model equation to predict the value of one variable given a specific value of the other variable (Egiyi & Okafor, 2022). Motor vehicles and intangible assets were the independent variables, whereas shareholders' funds were the dependent variable.

The multiple regression model adopted in this study is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \mu \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where: Y = stand for Shareholders' fund (the variable we are trying to predict);

β_0 = the intercept;

β_1 = coefficient of X_1 (the slope);

β_2 = coefficient of X_2 (the slope);

X_1 = Motor Vehicles (the variable used to predict Y);

X_2 = Intangible assets (the variable used to predict Y)

μ = the error term.

The intercept (β_0) is the value of the dependent variable when the independent variable is equal to zero, and the slope of the regression line ($\beta_1 - \beta_2$) represents the rate of change in Y as $X_1 - X_2$ changes. Because Y is dependent on $X_1 - X_2$, the slope describes the predicted values of Y given X_1 or X_2 . Adapting the above model in this study, it can be applied as stated in the model specification in Section 3.7.

3.7 Model Specifications

The following model was developed based on the variables used in the study:

The following model was developed based on the variables used in the study:

$$SHV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MV + \beta_2 InTA + \mu \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$MV = \frac{MV}{SHV} X \frac{100}{1} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

$$InTA = \frac{InTA}{SHV} X \frac{100}{1} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Where:

SHV = Shareholder Value

MV = Motor Vehicle,

InTA = Intangible assets

β = Beta,

μ = error margin.

$\beta_1 - \beta_n$, = proportionate change in dependent variable due to change in independent variables.

4.1 Results and Discussion

4.1.1 Determination, Estimation, and Hypothesis Test

The Hausman test was used to determine the appropriate model for testing the hypotheses, while the appropriate model was used in data analysis, and the hypotheses were tested using F-Statistics at a 5% level of significance. The Hausman test is a statistical procedure used to determine whether a fixed-effects or random-effects model is more appropriate for PDA. The Hausman test's null hypothesis posits that the preferred model is random effects, implying that the unique errors are uncorrelated with the regressors. The alternative hypothesis posits that the fixed-effects model is more suitable, indicating that the unique errors are correlated with the regressors. Panel data for this analysis comprised cross-sectional units (DMBs) observed over multiple periods (11 years). The overall dataset was structured as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

where:

Y_{it} represents the dependent variable (Shareholders' Value) for DMBs i in year t .

X_{it} represents the independent variable (MV, InTA) for DMBs i in a particular year t .

β_0 = the intercept.

β_1 = the coefficient of shareholders' factors of value.

μ_{it} = the error term.

4.1.2 Model Determination of Hypothesis 1

The Hausman test was conducted with the random-effects model against the fixed-effects model, ascertained by the probability at a 5% level of significance.

Model:

$$SHV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MV_{it} + u_i + \epsilon_{it} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

$$SHV = \beta_i + \beta_1 MV_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

Decision Rule:

H₀: The random effect (RE) model is appropriate.

H₁: The fixed effect (FE) model is appropriate

Table 4.1 Hausman test for Hypothesis 1

Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.*
Motor Vehicle	0.350000	0.429570	0.016650	0.5375
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d. f		Prob.*
Cross-section random	0.380268	1		0.5375

Source: Authors' computations

Analysis (Table 4.1) shows that the Hausman test results have a chi-square statistic of 0.380268 with a p-value of 0.5375. Because the p-value is much greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that no significant difference exists between the fixed and random effects estimates. This submits that the random-effects model is the more appropriate choice for this analysis. Comparing the estimates for motor vehicles, the fixed-effects coefficient is 0.350000, whereas the random-effects coefficient is 0.429570. The variance difference is 0.016650, and the probability value of 0.5375 confirms that these estimates are nearly identical.

Since the Hausman test posits that the random-effects model is more suitable, the random effects model should be used in the final analysis. This model is more efficient when no correlation exists between the independent variables (motor vehicle) and the observed firm-specific effects (shareholders' value), making it the best option for obtaining generalizable results.

4.1.3 Test of Hypothesis 1

H₀: Motor vehicles do not significantly affect shareholder value in Nigeria's DMBs

H₁: Motor vehicles significantly affect shareholder value in Nigeria's DMBs

Resultant Model:

$$SHV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MV_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Table 4.2 Panel data analysis results for Hypothesis One

Dependent Variable: Shareholder Value

Variable	Coefficient	St. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Constant	6.990000	1.446316	4.829629	0.0000
Motor Vehicle	0.350000	0.168156	2.089398	0.0432
Weighted Statistics				
R-Squared	0.751167	Alaska information crit.		1.176059
Adj. R-Squared	0.722890	Schwarz crit.		1.405522
S.E. of the reg	0.411897	Hannan-Quinn crit.		1.263453
F-Stat	26.56504	Durbin-Watson		1.050191
Prob (F-Stat.)	0.00000			

Source: Authors' computations

Analysis (Table 4.2) indicates that the dependent variable, SHV (shareholders' value), is influenced by the independent variable, MV (motor vehicle). The coefficient for MV is 0.3500, indicating that a 1% increase in market value is associated with a 35% increase in shareholder value, holding other factors constant. The p-value for motor vehicles is 0.0432, which is statistically significant at the 5% level, meaning that market value has a significant positive effect on the value of shareholders. The intercept (C) is 6.9900 and statistically significant ($p = 0.0000$), implying that the expected shareholders' value remains positive if the non-current asset (Motor Vehicle) as a variable is 0.

The R-squared value of 0.7512 means that 75.12% of the variations in SHV are explained by MV and the random effects. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.7229 confirms that the model fits well, even after adjusting for the number of predictors. The F-statistic of 26.56504 ($p = 0.0000$) shows that the model is overall significant, meaning that the fixed effects and motor vehicles significantly explain variations in shareholders' value. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.0502 means some level of positive autocorrelation in the residuals, but further diagnostics are needed to confirm this.

In summary, the non-current asset, MV, has a significant and positive effect on shareholders' value, meaning that companies whose MV asset value is high tend to achieve higher returns on shareholders' value. Since the Hausman test previously indicated that the random-effects model is appropriate, this interpretation is based on the most efficient and unbiased estimation. This finding is in agreement with Manafa *et al.* (2024), who stated that companies should increase their allocation of resources toward the acquisition of non-current assets.

The findings of this study are also supported by the study of Madukwe *et al.* (2022), who evaluated the effect of corporate assets on the market value of DMBs in Nigeria; Manafa (2023), who examined the effect of asset structure on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria; Onwaeze and Osuji (2024), who examined the asset management and financial performance of listed DBMs in Nigeria; and Gozie-Onu *et al.* (2024), who examined the effect of non-current assets on the shareholder's fund of DBMs in Nigeria. These studies concluded that various non-current assets, such as land and building, plant and machineries, and furniture and fittings, have a significant influence on the value of shareholders. However, the finding is not far from the opinions of Nangih and Emeka-Nwokeji (2021), Egwakhe *et al.* (2023), and Odoh *et al.* (2026) in maintaining that adequate measures must be put in place to guarantee that investments in all assets are properly mixed.

4.1.4 Determination of the Model of Hypothesis Two

The Hausman test was conducted with the random-effects model against the fixed effect model, ascertained by the probability at a 5% level of significance.

Model:

$$SHV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 InTA_{it} + u_i + \epsilon_{it} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

$$SHV = \beta_i + \beta_1 InTA_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

Decision Rule:

H₀: The random effect (RE) model is appropriate.

H₁: The fixed effect (FE) model is appropriate

Table 4.3 Hausman Test for Hypothesis Two

Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.*
Intangible Assets	0.175487	0.264655	0.001163	0.0089
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d. f.		Prob.*
Cross-section random	6.836414	1		0.0089

Source: Authors' computations

Analysis (Table 4.3) indicated that the Hausman test results showed a chi-square statistic of 6.836414 with a p-value of 0.0089. Because the p-value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the difference between the fixed and random effects estimates is significant. This indicates that the fixed-effects model is more appropriate for this analysis. Comparing the fixed and random effects estimates for intangible assets, the fixed and random effects coefficients are 0.175487 and 0.264655, respectively. The variance difference is 0.001163, and the probability value of 0.0089 confirms that these estimates differ significantly.

Since the Hausman test posits that the fixed-effects model is more reliable, the final analysis should use the fixed-effects model when examining the relationship between intangible assets and shareholder value. This choice accounts for unobserved heterogeneity and provides more consistent estimates, ensuring that the potential correlation between intangible assets and the non-current asset characteristics of an individual firm does not bias the results.

4.1.5 Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀: Intangible assets have no significant effect on the value of deposit money banks

H₁: Intangible assets have a significant effect on the value of deposit money banks

Resultant Model:

$$SHV = \beta_i + \beta_1 InTA_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Table 4.4 Panel data analysis results for Hypothesis Two**Dependent Variable: Shareholder Value**

Variables	Coefficient	St. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Constant	8.648747	0.519146	16.65956	0.0000
Intangible Assets	0.175487	0.067017	2.618550	0.0121
Weighted Statistics				
R-Squared	0.763519	Alaska information crit.		1.125164
Adj. R-Squared	0.736646	Schwarz crit.		1.354607
S.E. of the reg	0.401543	Hannan-Quinn crit.		1.212537
F-Stat	28.4123	Durbin-Watson		1.299322
Prob (F-Stat.)	0.000000			

Source: Authors' computations

Analysis (Table 4.4) indicated that the dependent variable, SHV, is influenced by the independent variable, InTA. The coefficient for intangible assets is 0.1755, meaning that a 1% increase in intangible assets is associated with a 17.55% increase in the value of shareholders, holding other factors constant. The p-value for IAs is 0.0121, which is statistically significant at the 5% level, indicating that IAs have a significant positive effect on the value

of shareholders. The intercept (Constant) is 8.6487 and statistically significant ($p = 0.0000$), implying that the expected shareholders' value remains positive when the independent asset is zero.

The R-squared value of 0.7635 means that 76.35% of the variations in SV are explained by InTA and the fixed effects. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.7366 confirms that the model fits well, even after adjusting for the number of predictors. The F-statistic of 28.4123 ($p = 0.0000$) suggests that the model is statistically significant overall, indicating that variations in shareholders' value are significantly explained by independent assets, along with the fixed effects. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.2993 means a low likelihood of severe autocorrelation in the residuals, implying a good fit.

In summary, as a non-current asset, intangible assets have a significant and positive effect on shareholder value, meaning that firms with higher intangible assets tend to achieve higher returns on shareholder value. Since the Hausman test previously indicated that the fixed-effects model is appropriate, this interpretation is based on the most efficient and unbiased estimation. While this finding contradicts Okobo et al. (2022) in their study of investment in tangible non-current assets and financial performance of food manufacturing firms in Nigeria, which insinuates that investments on tangible non-current assets are more profitable, it agrees with the findings of Chukwu et al. (2017), Awa et al. (2020), Charlie & Akpan (2020), and Akpekon (2021). In their separate studies, these authors advocate for no less investment in intangible assets like patents, goodwill, and licenses. While agreeing that other factors, such as profitability, operational efficiency, and market conditions, as suggested by Egwu et al. (2023), play their roles in the shareholders' value, the present study emphasizes that investment in intangible assets is worth any kobo invested.

5. Conclusions, Caveats, and Future Research Directions

Summary of the Findings

Having examined the effect of two major non-current assets, motor vehicles and intangible assets, on shareholders' value, the results indicate the following

1. The acquisition of motor vehicles by DMBs significantly affects shareholders' value in banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, as shown by the coefficient and p values ($\beta = 0.350000$; $p < 0.05$).
2. In addition, intangible assets had a statistically significant effect on shareholders' value in banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange ($\beta = 0.175487$; $p < 0.05$). This simply entails that both asset measures have a significant influence and should be invested more in DMBs.

Conclusion

This study examined the effect of asset structure on the value of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The findings revealed that motor vehicles demonstrated a statistically significant positive effect on the value of shareholders. This finding shows that MVEs play a crucial role in enhancing operational efficiency and profitability, ultimately benefiting shareholders. Similarly, intangible assets had a statistically significant positive effect on the value of shareholders. This underscores the importance of IP, goodwill, and proprietary technologies in driving financial performance and creating value for shareholders.

Recommendations

- i. Deposit money banks should continue investing in MVEs to enhance transportation and logistics efficiency, which plays a crucial role in operational effectiveness and shareholder returns.
- ii. Deposit money banks should prioritize investment in intangible assets such as goodwill, patents, proprietary technologies, and brand equity to strengthen their competitive advantage and drive long-term shareholder value.

Disclosure statement

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